

DESCRIPTION OF REGIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE CLINICAL COURSE OF COVID-19-ASSOCIATED LUNG INJURY DEPENDING ON AGE

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Acute Respiratory Syndrome – related Coronavirus – 2 (SARS-Cov-2) and respiratory disorders has been shown [24, 15, 23, 14].

ABSTRACT

The global spread of COVID-19, the novel coronavirus disease, began in December 2019 and was declared a pandemic by the WHO. In a short period of time, as of May 10, 2020, COVID-19 had spread to more than 3 million people in 166 countries. During this period, dedicated research has been conducted, manuals and numerous publications have been published, and practical activities have been intensified [2, 3, 6, 11, 4].

Introduction. The global spread of COVID-19, the novel coronavirus disease, began in December 2019 and was declared a pandemic by the WHO. In a short period of time, as of May 10, 2020, COVID-19 had spread to more than 3 million people in 166 countries. During this period, dedicated research has been conducted, manuals and numerous publications have been published, and practical activities have been intensified [2, 3, 6, 11, 4].

At the same time, it is possible to “take a lead” from scientific sources that existing clinical studies have shown very important results and that preventive directions, especially in the case of COVID-19, can be shown in general [4, 18, 10, 1, 7, 19].

Respiratory disorders caused by COVID-19 manifest in various forms and persist long after the COVID infection has resolved as a post-COVID syndrome (PS) [13].

According to Woodruff P. et al. (2016), Song W.J. et al. (2021), Venka-tesan P. (2021) and Richardson S. et al. (2020), coronaviruses are considered one of the main risk factors for lung damage, especially bronchoobstructive syndrome (BOS), due to their “inducing” properties. An association between Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome – related Coronavirus – 2 (SARS-Cov-2) and respiratory disorders has been shown [24, 15, 23, 14].

Therefore, it is important to study the epidemiology, clinical manifestations, pharmacotherapy, and modern aspects of prevention of lung damage caused by COVID-19. This is precisely the opinion, conclusions, and recommendations that are reflected in recent studies and scientific sources during and after the COVID-19 period [12, 5, 14, 8, 17, 16, 9].

The fact that extensive research has been conducted in this context is also evident from the literature review. The data presented by the researchers confirm, in particular, that various treatment methods are currently being developed or approved for coronavirus infection and associated diseases, including patients with COVID-19 b OS [21, 20, 22].

Based on the review of the literature on the chapter, it can be concluded that at present, COVID-19 associated lung injury remains one of the most important and multifaceted, mainly epidemiological problems. It is necessary to develop technologies for early detection of various clinical forms of COVID-19 associated lung injury, eliminate the iatrogenic risk of pharmacotherapy, and predict the risk of severe disease. Significant scientific research in this direction is being paid special attention worldwide. There is an urgent need and necessity to conduct separate epidemiological studies on the epidemiology, premorbid and morbid background, clinical manifestations, pharmacoepidemiology and search for effective prevention methods of lung damage with COVID-19 on a global scale, including in the territory of Uzbekistan. Such studies have not been conducted in Uzbekistan and there is no data. In this direction, the creation of an optimal model and system of preventive medicine, as shown by the analysis of the literature, is an urgent scientific problem both on a global scale and in Uzbekistan. The results obtained in this way will bring medical, social and economic benefits, almost eliminating medical disasters and reducing costs by several orders of magnitude.

The aim of the study is to study the prevalence, premorbid background, clinical manifestations, and pharmacoepidemiology of lung injury with COVID-19, and to identify effective prevention methods.

Material and methods

Object of research Venous blood and serum from patients infected with COVID-19 were collected for biochemical and immunological tests.

Research methods: The research uses epidemiological, clinical, instrumental, laboratory, immunological, and statistical research methods.

Results

The description of the regional characteristics of the clinical course of COVID-19-associated lung injury depending on age is shown in Table 1 and Figure 1.

The data in the table and figure show that the expression of clinical manifestations of COVID-19-associated lung injury depending on age is confirmed in the conditions of Andijan with the following frequencies of detection: 1) mild pneumonia, respectively, in 18-24 year olds - 37.6%, in 25-44 - 37.7%, in 18-74 year olds - 37.7%, in 45-59 - 37.7%, in 60-74 - 38.0% and in 45-74 year olds - 37.8% ($P > 0.05$);

2) severe pneumonia - 22.3% in 18-24 years, 22.4% in 25-44 years, total - 22.3% in 18-44 years, 22.3% in 45-59 years, 22.3% in 60-74 years and 22.2% in 45-74 years [$P > 0.05$]; 3) pneumonia with acute respiratory failure - 6.4% in 18-24 years, 6.4% in 25-44 years, 6.4% in 18-44 years, 6.4% in 45-59 years, 6.2% in 60-74 years and 6.3% in 45-74 years [$RR = 0.98$; 95% $CI = 0.66-1.46$; $p > 0.05$]; 4) pneumonia without acute respiratory failure - 23.8%, 25-44 - 23.4%, 18-44 - 23.7%, 45-59 - 23.7%, 60-74 - 23.3% and 45-74 - 23.5% [$RR = 0.99$; 95% $CI = 0.87-1.20$; $p > 0.05$]; 5) pneumonia with acute respiratory distress syndrome - 6.9% at 18-24 years, 7.0% at 25-44, 7.0% at 18-44, 7.1% at 45-59, 6.8% at 60-74, and 7.0% at 45-74 [$RR = 1.0$; 95% $CI = 0.68 - 1.46$; $p > 0.05$]; 6) option of pneumonia with sepsis - 3.0% at 18-24, 3.0% at 25-44, 3.0% at 18-44, 3.0% at 45-59, 3.0% at 60-74, and 3.0% at 45-74 [$RR = 1.0$; 95% $CI = 0.57 - 1.76$; $p > 0.05$]; 7) "Pneumonia+BA" variant clinical course - 5.2% at 18-44, 5.1% at 25-44, 5.2% at 18-44, 5.0% at 45-59, 5.3% at 60-74 and 5.1% at 45-74 years

old [RR=0.99; 95% CI=0.65 - 1.49; p>0.05]; 8) The prevalence of “Pneumonia+AS” comorbidity is characterized by the following frequencies: 18–24 years – 6.9%, 25–44 years – 6.8%, 18–44 years – 6.9%, 45–59 years – 7.1%, 60–74 years – 6.8% and 45–74 years – 7.1%, 60–74 years – 6.8% and 45–74 years – 7.0% [RR=1.01; 95% CI=0.71–1.45; p>0.05].

The results show that the majority of COVID-19-associated lung damage, in the form of pneumonia and pneumonia without acute respiratory syndrome, was observed in 25–44 years old.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, a mathematical model was created to assess the role of premorbid (overweight, hypertension, smoking, physical inactivity, AI) and comorbid background (bronchial asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, urinary tract diseases, anemia, endocrine diseases) in the occurrence of COVID-19-associated lung injury, and their predictive characteristics were determined using this model.

On this basis, the risks of COVID-19-associated lung injury at “very high”, “high”, “low” and very low levels were predicted and confirmed. The prevention program “Effective optimized way of preventing COVID-19-associated lung injury (on the example of the Fergana Valley)” was created and recommended for practice..

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